

Amplify-and-Forward Virtual Full-Duplex Relaying Based Cooperative NOMA

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Abstract—This letter studies the performance of a virtual full-duplex relaying technique in cooperative non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA)-based systems. In particular, two half-duplex amplify-and-forward relays imitate the operation of full-duplex relaying in cooperative NOMA systems using the successive relaying (SR) technique, in order to recover the loss of spectral efficiency due to the half-duplex constraint at the relays. The closed-form outage probability of the proposed scheme is derived. The simulation results show that the proposed SR based cooperative NOMA system with an opportunistic power split factor achieves a lower outage probability and a higher ergodic rate than the existing SR based orthogonal multiple access (OMA) system and ideal full duplex relaying based NOMA systems.

Index Terms—Non-orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA), amplify-and-forward (AF), successive relaying (SR).

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional multiple access techniques, i.e., orthogonal multiple access (OMA), is used in Internet of Things (IoT) applications, such as smart homes, which require abundant of orthogonal channels in connecting sensors, devices and appliances. This could be very challenging with the limited channel resource and the orthogonal channels result in loss of spectral efficiency. Recently, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) technique has been proposed as a promising multiple access technique. With the NOMA technique, multiple users or devices can be served at the same time/code/frequency block, but with different power level. Therefore, the spectral efficiency can be improved.

The NOMA technique can be extended to a relaying assisted network. Relay assisted NOMA system was proposed to improve the reception reliability [1]. However, most of the relay assisted NOMA systems adopt the half-duplex (HD) cooperation mechanism. Due to the HD cooperation mechanism, every transmission from the source to the destination needs two time slots. Therefore, additional channel resources are required for the relay cooperation technique compared to typical NOMA systems without relays. The improvement of reception reliability brought by the cooperative NOMA technique comes at a price of reduced spectral efficiency. This diverges from the original purpose of NOMA techniques,

i.e., to improve the spectral efficiency. In [2], the full-duplex (FD) cooperative NOMA scheme is proposed to overcome the spectral efficiency loss inherent to the HD cooperative NOMA systems. However, the system design complexity of FD relaying is a major concern for practical implementation due to the self-interference cancellation requirement. Hence, conventional HD relaying is more practical than FD relaying. Alternatively, a virtual full-duplex relay in [3] with the successive relaying (SR) technique can be used. A pair of HD relays are used in the SR to imitate the operation of FD relaying. The pair of HD relays work alternately as the receiver and transmitter that enables the source to continuously transmit data to the destination without incurring additional channel resources or time slots.

In this letter, we propose a SR based cooperative NOMA (SR-NOMA) system, where a pair of amplify-and-forward (AF) HD relays assist the transmission from source to users. In addition, the closed-form outage probability of the proposed SR-NOMA system is derived. The proposed SR-NOMA employs AF relays instead of decode-and-forward (DF) relays since the AF relays have the advantage of lower complexity and more flexibility in handling the inter-relay interference (IRI).¹ As shown in the numerical results, the users in the proposed SR-NOMA system achieve a lower outage probability and a higher ergodic rate than the existing SR based OMA system (SR-OMA) and the ideal DF FD relaying based NOMA system (IFR-NOMA).

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This letter considers a cognitive radio scenario as in [6], where a primary user D_a is given higher priority to achieve its quality-of-service (QoS) than a secondary user D_b . The system consists of a source (S), a pair of AF HD relays (R_i) and two users (D_j) as shown in Fig. 1, where the subscripts denote $i = \{1, 2\}$ and $j = \{a, b\}$. It is assumed that there is no direct channel between the source and the users. The source-relays, relays-users and inter-relay channels experience independent and identically quasi-static Rayleigh fading. We assume that all the channels are reciprocal, static for a transmission block,

¹In presence of IRI, the DF relay decodes the data from the source by treating the IRI as noise or performs successive interference cancellation by decoding the IRI first [4]. Therefore, the IRI has to be extremely weaker or stronger than the transmitted signal from the source. Meanwhile, for the AF relay, the IRI can be canceled by subtracting the previous received signal at the destination regardless of the IRI condition [5].

Fig. 1. A cooperative NOMA system using the successive relaying (SR) technique.

i.e., $N + 1$ time slots, and change independently between transmission blocks.

As shown in Fig. 1, the transmission protocol of SR is divided into even time slot (n) and odd time slot ($n + 1$). At even time slot (n), S transmits a superimposed mixture, $x_s(n)$ to R_2 . The superimposed mixture transmitted by S is

$$x_s(n) = \sqrt{\alpha} x_a(n) + \sqrt{\beta} x_b(n),$$

containing signals $x_a(n)$ and $x_b(n)$ for the D_a and the D_b , respectively, where α and β denote the power split factors. At the same time, the R_1 transmits $x_1(n) = G_1 y_1(n - 1)$ to the D_j , where $y_1(n - 1)$ is the previous received signal at R_1 and G_1 is the amplifying factor of R_1 . The amplifying factor of R_i is denoted by $G_i^2 = \frac{P_r}{P_s |h_{si}|^2 + P_r |h_r|^2 + \sigma^2}$, where P_r , h_{si} and h_r are the unity transmit power of relays, the gain of the source-relays and the inter-relay channels, respectively. Therefore, the received signal at R_2 and D_j are given as

$$y_2(n) = h_{s2} x_s(n) + h_r x_1(n) + w_2, \quad (1)$$

$$y_j(n) = h_{1j} x_1(n) + w_j, \quad (2)$$

respectively, where w_i and w_j are the noise at R_i and D_j , respectively.

At odd time slot ($n+1$), R_1 receives $x_s(n+1)$ and $x_2(n+1)$ from the S and R_2 , respectively, which is given as

$$y_1(n+1) = h_{s1} x_s(n+1) + h_r x_2(n+1) + w_1, \quad (3)$$

where $x_2(n+1) = G_2 y_2(n)$. At the same time, D_j receives $x_2(n+1)$ from the R_2 which is given as

$$\begin{aligned} y_j(n+1) &= h_{2j} x_2(n+1) + w_j \\ &= h_{2j} G_2 y_2(n) + w_j \\ &= \underbrace{h_{2j} G_2 h_{s2} x_s(n)}_{\text{desired signal}} + \underbrace{h_{2j} G_2 h_r x_1(n)}_{\text{IRI}} \\ &\quad + \underbrace{h_{2j} G_2 w_2 + w_j}_{\text{noise}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $y_2(n)$ is the received signal at R_2 during even time slot (n) which is given in (1).

In order to cancel the IRI, the full interference cancellation (FIC) algorithm in [5] is employed. By manipulating (2), we have

$$x_1(n) = \frac{y_j(n) - w_j}{h_{1j}}. \quad (5)$$

Substituting (5) into (4) gives:

$$y_j(n+1) = h_{2j} G_2 h_{s2} x_s(n) + \frac{h_{2j} G_2 h_r}{h_{1j}} y_j(n) + w_{j,o}^*, \quad (6)$$

where $y_j(n)$ is the previous received signal and the noise term $w_{j,o}^* = h_{2j} G_2 w_2 + \frac{h_{1j} - h_{2j} G_2 h_r}{h_{1j}} w_j$. It is obvious that the IRI appears as the second term of the right-hand-side in (6). Therefore, the IRI in the received signal of D_j during odd time slot ($n + 1$) can be canceled by subtracting $\frac{h_{2j} G_2 h_r}{h_{1j}} y_j(n)$ from (6). We assume the D_j knows the channel state information (CSI) of every channels. By applying the FIC algorithm, the received signal at D_j during even time slot (n) and odd time slot ($n + 1$) can be rewritten as

$$y_j^*(n) = h_{1j} G_1 h_{s1} x_s(n-1) + w_{j,e}^*, \quad (7)$$

$$y_j^*(n+1) = h_{2j} G_2 h_{s2} x_s(n) + w_{j,o}^*, \quad (8)$$

where the noise term $w_{j,e}^* = h_{1j} G_1 w_1 + \frac{h_{2j} - h_{1j} G_1 h_r}{h_{2j}} w_j$.

For notation simplicity, we assume $P_s = P_r = 1$, the noise variances for all of the channels are same, i.e., $\sigma_i^2 = \sigma_j^2 = \sigma^2$, and the same fading variance from source to both relays and from both relays to the both destination, i.e., $E[|h_{si}|^2] = \nu_s$, $E[|h_{ij}|^2] = \nu_d$. Based on (7), the instantaneous rates of D_a during even time slot (n) can be obtained as:

$$C_a(n) = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{1a}}{\beta \varepsilon_{1a} + \gamma(|h_{1a}|^2 + |h_{s1}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right), \quad (9)$$

where the average SNR $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$, $\varepsilon_{1a} = \gamma^2 |h_{1a}|^2 |h_{s1}|^2$ and $\delta_r = 2\gamma |h_r|^2$. Meanwhile, the instantaneous rate of D_b during even time slot (n) can be obtained as:

$$C_b(n) = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta \varepsilon_{1b}}{\gamma(|h_{1b}|^2 + |h_{s1}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right), \quad (10)$$

conditioned on $\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{1b}}{\beta \varepsilon_{1b} + \gamma(|h_{1b}|^2 + |h_{s1}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right) \geq r_a$, where $\varepsilon_{1b} = \gamma^2 |h_{1b}|^2 |h_{s1}|^2$ and r_j is the target rate of D_j .

On the other hand, based on (8), the instantaneous rates of D_a during odd time slot ($n + 1$) can be obtained as follows:

$$C_a(n+1) = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{2a}}{\beta \varepsilon_{2a} + \gamma(|h_{2a}|^2 + |h_{s2}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right), \quad (11)$$

where $\varepsilon_{2a} = \gamma^2 |h_{2a}|^2 |h_{s2}|^2$. Meanwhile, the instantaneous rates of D_b during odd time slot ($n + 1$) can be obtained as follows:

$$C_b(n+1) = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta \varepsilon_{2b}}{\gamma(|h_{2b}|^2 + |h_{s2}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right), \quad (12)$$

conditioned on $\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{2b}}{\beta \varepsilon_{2b} + \gamma(|h_{2b}|^2 + |h_{s2}|^2) + \delta_r + 1} \right) \geq r_a$, where $\varepsilon_{2b} = \gamma^2 |h_{2b}|^2 |h_{s2}|^2$.

The transmission is repeated until N frames have been transmitted from the S . A total of $(N + 1)$ time slots are needed because D_j receives no signal at the first time slot. Assume that the S knows the CSI and encodes the signals over $(N + 1)$ time slots. The ergodic rate of D_j assisted by the SR in cooperative NOMA system, C_j , can be attained as follows [7]:

$$C_j = \min\left(\frac{N}{2(N+1)}(C_j(n) + C_j(n+1)), r_j\right), \quad (13)$$

where N is the total transmitted frames by S and r_j is the target rate of D_j .

A. Opportunistic power split factor

In this letter, α and β denote the power split factor of D_a and D_b in the NOMA system, respectively. Unlike [6] and [8] that apply a fixed power split factor, this letter proposes an opportunistic power split factor. Initially, the power split factor of D_a and D_b are fixed at $\alpha = 0.9$ and $\beta = 0.1$, respectively. However, when D_a can achieve its target rate, r_a , with less power, i.e., $\alpha < 0.9$, β is increased, i.e., $\beta = 1 - \alpha$. With the opportunistic power split factor, the performance of D_b can be improved opportunistically without degrading the performance of D_a . From (13), the equality where D_a achieves r_a is given as

$$\frac{N}{2(N+1)}(C_a(n) + C_a(n+1)) = r_a. \quad (14)$$

By substituting $\beta = 1 - \alpha$ into (14) and with some algebraic manipulations, (14) is expressed in the following quadratic equation,

$$q \varepsilon_{1a} \varepsilon_{2a} \alpha^2 - \nu \alpha + (q-1)m_1 m_2 = 0, \quad (15)$$

where $q = 2^{2r_a}$, $\varepsilon_{ia} = \gamma^2 |h_{ia}|^2 |h_{si}|^2$, $m_i = \varepsilon_{ia} + \gamma(|h_{ia}|^2 + |h_{si}|^2) + \delta_r + 1$ and $\nu = q(\varepsilon_{1a} m_2 + \varepsilon_{2a} m_1)$. By solving the quadratic equation in (15) with quadratic formula, α is obtained as follows

$$\alpha = \frac{\nu - \sqrt{\nu^2 - 4q \varepsilon_{1a} \varepsilon_{2a} \mu}}{2q \varepsilon_{1a} \varepsilon_{2a}}, \quad (16)$$

where $\mu = (q-1)m_1 m_2$ and $\alpha \leq 0.9$. Recall that all channels remain static for a transmission block, i.e., $N+1$ time slots. Therefore, α and β throughout a transmission block are fixed.

III. ANALYSIS OF OUTAGE PROBABILITIES

This section characterizes the outage probabilities of D_j assisted by the proposed SR-NOMA scheme.

Theorem 1. *The closed-form outage probabilities of D_j using the proposed SR-NOMA scheme can be expressed as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\mathcal{O}_a) &= \Pr(C_a < r_a) \\ &= \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_a}{2\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)}\right) - \frac{2\tau_a}{\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)} \exp\left(\frac{3\tau_a}{2\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)}\right) \text{Ei}\left(-\frac{2\tau_a}{\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)}\right) \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\mathcal{O}_b) &= \Pr(C_b < r_b) \\ &= \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_b}{2\gamma\beta}\right) - \frac{2\tau_b}{\gamma\beta} \exp\left(-\frac{3\tau_b}{2\gamma\beta}\right) \text{Ei}\left(-\frac{2\tau_b}{\gamma\beta}\right) \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $j = \{a, b\}$, $\tau_j = 2^{\phi_j} - 1$, $\phi_j = \frac{2(N+1)r_j}{N}$, $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$ and $\text{Ei}(x)$ denotes the exponential integral.

Proof: The overall outage event of D_j can be categorized as follows:

$$\mathcal{O}_j = \mathcal{O}_n \cap \mathcal{O}_{n+1}, \quad (19)$$

where \mathcal{O}_n denotes the event that $\frac{N}{2(N+1)}C_j(n) \leq r_j$ during even time slots and \mathcal{O}_{n+1} denotes the event that $\frac{N}{2(N+1)}C_j(n+1) \leq r_j$ during odd time slots, respectively. Based on the (19), the outage probability of D_j can be written as follows:

$$\Pr(\mathcal{O}_j) = \Pr(\mathcal{O}_n) \times \Pr(\mathcal{O}_{n+1}). \quad (20)$$

The term $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_n)$ of D_a can be calculated as $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_n) = 1 - \Pr(\frac{N}{2(N+1)}C_a(n) \geq r_a)$. By applying the high SNR assumption and some algebraic manipulations, the term $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_n)$ of D_a can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\mathcal{O}_n) &= 1 - \Pr\left(\frac{N}{2(N+1)}C_a(n) \geq r_a\right) \\ &\approx 1 - \Pr\left(\frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{1a}}{\beta \varepsilon_{1a} + \gamma(|h_{1a}|^2 + |h_{s1}|^2) + \delta_r} \geq \tau_a\right) \\ &= 1 - \Pr\left(\alpha \varepsilon_{1a} - \tau_a(\beta \varepsilon_{1a} + \gamma |h_{s1}|^2) \geq \tau_a(\gamma |h_{1a}|^2 + \delta_r)\right) \\ &= 1 - \Pr\left(|h_{s1}|^2 \geq \frac{\tau_a}{\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)} \left(\frac{|h_{1a}|^2 + \delta_r}{|h_{1a}|^2 - \frac{\tau_a}{\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)}}\right)\right) \\ &= 1 - \Pr\left(|h_{s1}|^2 \geq \Psi_a \left(\frac{|h_{1a}|^2 + \delta_r}{|h_{1a}|^2 - \Psi_a}\right)\right) \\ &= 1 - \Pr\left(|h_{s1}|^2 \geq \Psi_a \left(\frac{|h_{1a}|^2 + 2\gamma |h_r|^2}{|h_{1a}|^2 - \Psi_a}\right)\right) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^\infty \exp(-z) \int_{\Psi_a}^\infty \exp(-y) \int_{\Psi_a \left(\frac{y+2z}{y-\Psi_a}\right)}^\infty \exp(-x) dx dy dz \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} 1 - \exp(-\Psi_a) \int_0^\infty \exp(-z) \sqrt{\omega} K_1(\sqrt{\omega}) \\ &= 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Psi_a}{2}\right) - 2\Psi_a \exp\left(\frac{3\Psi_a}{2}\right) \text{Ei}(-2\Psi_a), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $\tau_a = 2^{\phi_a} - 1$, $\phi_a = \frac{2(N+1)r_a}{N}$, $\Psi_a = \frac{\tau_a}{\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)}$, $\omega = 4\Psi_a(2z + \Psi_a)$, $K_1(\cdot)$ is the first-order modified Bessel function of the second kind and step (a) is obtained with the aid of (3.324.1) in [9]. Meanwhile, $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_{n+1}) = \Pr(\mathcal{O}_n)$ due to the independent and identically distributed channels assumption. By substituting (21) into (20), $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_a)$ is obtained. On the other hand, the $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_n)$ of D_b can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\mathcal{O}_n) &\approx 1 - \Pr\left(\frac{\beta \gamma^2 |h_{1b}|^2 |h_{s1}|^2}{\gamma(|h_{1b}|^2 + |h_{s1}|^2) + \delta_r} > \tau_b\right) \\ &= 1 - \Pr\left(|h_{s2}|^2 \geq \Psi_b \left(\frac{|h_{2a}|^2 + \delta_r}{|h_{2a}|^2 - \Psi_b}\right)\right) \\ &= 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Psi_b}{2}\right) - 2\Psi_b \exp\left(\frac{3\Psi_b}{2}\right) \text{Ei}(-2\Psi_b), \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\Psi_b = \frac{\tau_b}{\beta\gamma}$, $\tau_b = 2^{\phi_b} - 1$ and $\phi_b = \frac{2(N+1)r_b}{N}$. Similarly to $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_a)$, by substituting (22) into (20), $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_b)$ is obtained and Theorem 1 is proved. ■

Remark 2. By using the high SNR approximation, i.e., $\sigma^2 \rightarrow 0$, the third term of the right-hand-side in (17) and (18) can be ignored, and with the approximation for the exponent, i.e.,

$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \exp(-x) = 1 - x$, $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_a)$ and $\Pr(\mathcal{O}_b)$ in Theorem 1 can be approximated as follows

$$\mathcal{P}_a \approx \left(\frac{\tau_a}{2\gamma(\alpha - \tau_a\beta)} \right)^2, \quad (23)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_b \approx \left(\frac{\tau_b}{2\gamma\beta} \right)^2, \quad (24)$$

respectively. The definition of diversity order is given as $-\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log(\mathcal{P}_e)}{\log \gamma}$ in [10], where \mathcal{P}_e is the outage probability. Since $-\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log(\mathcal{P}_j)}{\log \gamma} = 2$, therefore the diversity order achieved by the SR at user D_j is 2.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this letter, the target rate of primary user (D_a) and secondary user (D_b) are fixed at $r_a = 0.6$ bits/s/Hz and $r_b = 3$ bits/s/Hz, respectively, and $N = 1000$. Figs. 2 and 3 compare the performance of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme, existing SR-OMA scheme in [3] and IFR-NOMA scheme in [2] assisted by a DF-FD relay.² In IFR-NOMA scheme, the self interference is assumed to be completely canceled with no residual. Fig. 2 shows the outage probability of D_a and D_b in various schemes. The proposed SR-NOMA scheme achieves the lowest outage probability if compared to SR-OMA and IFR-NOMA schemes. This justifies that the proposed SR-NOMA scheme offers the best reception reliability at the users than SR-OMA and IFR-NOMA schemes. The achievable rate of the IFR-NOMA scheme assisted by the DF-FD relay is limited by the worst source-relay and relay-users channels. As a results, the outage probability of the IFR-NOMA scheme is higher than the proposed SR-NOMA scheme. Meanwhile, the closed form of the outage probabilities match well with the numerical results of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme. Therefore, the closed form of outage probabilities of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme are verified.

On the other hand, Fig. 3 shows the ergodic rate of D_a and D_b in various schemes. The users of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme achieves higher ergodic rates than SR-OMA and IFR-NOMA schemes. Moreover, when SNR = 10dB and 30dB, D_a and D_b of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme achieve r_a and r_b , respectively. When SNR \leq 10dB, the IFR-NOMA scheme fails since the DF-FD relay cannot decode the messages successfully. Meanwhile, the IFR-NOMA scheme requires a higher SNR for the D_a and D_b to achieve their target rates, i.e., SNR= 35dB and 40dB, respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This letter proposed AF SR based NOMA system. The proposed SR-NOMA scheme achieves a lower outage probability and a higher ergodic rate than existing SR-OMA and IFR-NOMA schemes. The closed form outage probability of the proposed SR-NOMA scheme was developed and also verified.

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Fig. 2. Comparison of outage probability among various schemes.

Fig. 3. Comparison of ergodic rate among various schemes.

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²The DF-FD relay outperforms an AF-FD relay since the distortion-loop of the AF-DF relay degrades its performance [11].